

Silica fibers production and characterization for future gravitational waves detectors

Matteo Montani^{1,2} on behalf of the Virgo Collaboration

¹ University of Urbino Via S. Chiara 27, 61029 Urbino Italy

² INFN Firenze Via Sansone 1, 50019 Sesto Fiorentino

April 2, 2020

Abstract

The observation of gravitational waves is highly influenced by the detectors sensitivity, that is limited at low frequencies (10 -100 Hz) by the thermal noise. For this reason, the monolithic suspensions are one of the most important upgrades of the interferometric detectors including Advanced Ligo (aLigo) and Advanced Virgo (AdV). Currently the silica fibers are built to minimize the thermal noise in the band of interest and to fit the load constraints. Nevertheless, the need to have larger reference masses for the future updates of Virgo and also for the future 3G detectors at room temperature, requires redesigning the fibers, and all the facilities for their production, testing and characterization, for instance the fibers for Advanced Virgo Plus (AdV+) will be 60% thicker to deal with a working load 2.5 times higher. We will describe the manufacturing system, the nominal characteristics and the mechanical measurements of AdV's silica fibers, as well as the updates to improve the production and characterization process for the new specifications of AdV+. Finally an approach to the study of fatigue for silica fibers will be presented; the study of the behavior of pristine fibers is important to achieve a consistent model of lifetime prediction for maintenance and security reasons.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3555211

Introduction

Gravitational wave interferometers are subject to a wide variety of noises that limit their sensitivity, in particular, to reduce thermal noise, both Advanced Ligo (aLIGO) and AdV share the choice of having a multi-stage pendulums system ending with the monolithic suspension, a final pendulum stage made entirely by fused silica. The use of silica fibers is essential in noise reduction, and to increase the sensitivity of the instrument, especially at low frequencies (under 30 Hz). With respects to the other possible materials, silica fibers present low mechanical losses, and the cancellation of the thermoelastic noise [1], they also demonstrate an extraordinary resistance to traction, i.e. for AdV, four fibers have to support the weight of 42 kg. In addition their breaking load should be 4 times the working load, to guarantee a wide margin of safety. The technology developed in recent years has granted the construction of fibers that meet the requirements of resistance and furthermore that have bouncing frequencies below 10 Hz and the first order of violin frequencies above 440 Hz, so that for a wide frequency region there are no resonances that would reduce the sensitivity of the instruments.

The evolution of the gravitational wave interferometers necessarily implies the reduction of thermal noise and different strategies have been planned for the future: for instance the research on the coating mirror thermal noise, or the decrease of the temperature for the future 3G detectors. The strategy of AdV+ involves also the use of larger and heavier test masses and this choice has a strong impact on the entire suspension and obviously on the silica fibers. The manufacturing system used for AdV must be updated to meet the future specifications of AdV+, but also the fibers characterization remains an issue, because the high weight at which they have to be tested requires a redesign of the facilities.

Even though the silica fibers and their mechanical properties have been largely studied in the past year [2][3], it's not yet available a reliable model that describes the aging of pristine fibers in relation to the fatigue. This result would be useful to estimate the lifetime of a fiber, a crucial information for maintenance, but also important to design the best testing procedure to ensure an adequate strength without significantly damaging the fibers. Starting from a single region power-law model [4], we propose the study of the behavior of the fibers subjected to fatigue in order to validate the model and extrapolate the parameters.

AdV fibers fabrication and characterization

The monolithic suspension of Advanced Virgo (AdV) is made using four silica fibers with a dumb-bell shaped profile, having a diameter of 800 μm for 20 mm at the fiber terminations, and 400 μm for the remaining length (Figure 1). The length of the fiber is 700 mm from the center of mass of the marionette to the center of mass of the reference mass. The fiber's shape is designed with the 800 μm sections in order to reduce the thermoelastic noise[1].

Production procedure

The machine used to produce the fibers (fiber pulling machine) is schematized in Figure 2a. The beam of a 200 W CO_2 laser is deflected by 2 rotating mirrors that rotate at 340 rpm, generating a beam which is conveyed onto the silica rod by a conical mirror.

Considering that the absorption coefficient of the fused Silica at wavelength of our laser ($\lambda = 10.6\mu m$) is $\sim 0.8 \cdot 10^5 m^{-1}$ [5], the power emitted by the laser is absorbed by the silica rod, which increases its temperature. The conic mirror is mounted on a moving arm, allowing to change the vertical heating position. Another moving arm clamps the upper part of the rod to allow pulling the fiber. The whole fiber production process consists in three main steps:

- the two ends of the rod are welded to two silica components called anchors (Figure 2b, 2d).
- The rod is laser polished to remove superficial cracks (speed 0,03 mm/s; power $\sim 25W$)(Figure 2c).
- The fiber is pulled (power $\sim 35 W$), and the desired profile is obtained by controlling the speed and position of the upper clamp and of the melting point. Higher speed of the clamp arm is used for the thinner parts of the fiber; to obtain the diameter of 0.400mm the speed is 30mm/s for the clamp and 0.53mm/s for the mirror.

Figure 1: Dumbbell profile of a fiber of the AdV suspension system.

Figure 2: (a) Scheme of the fiber pulling machine. (b) The welding sequence between rod and an anchor. (c) Laser polishing of the silica rod. (d) The design of an anchor.

Mirror	Inclination of EAR-A	Inclination of EAR-B	Residual Mirror Inclination
NE	1 mrad UP	5 mrad UP	0.4 mrad UP
WE	1.6 mrad DOWN	5 mrad UP	0.7 mrad DOWN
NI	-	-	< 0.5 mrad UP
WI	1.3 mrad DOWN	0.5 mrad UP	0.8 mrad DOWN

Table 1: The vertical inclination of the mirrors of AdV measured after the fiber installation (residual mirror inclination). The EAR-A and EAR-B are the left and right silica components (glued to the mirrors) that connect the fibers to the mirror. Their inclination refers to the measure of the angle after the silica bonding with the mirrors, before the fibers installation.

Figure 3: Length and Elastic Coefficient of the AdV fibers.

Characterization

The length of the fibers mounted on AdV have been measured under different loads to extract their length in working condition and their elastic coefficient. The results, described by the charts in Figure 4, show that the manufacturing process has a very high repeatability, which is essential to meet the constraints on the residual vertical inclination of the mirrors which must be less than 2 mrad. The fiber assembly procedure involves the production of 8 fibers to be able to choose the ones most suitable. Since the ears (the pieces of fused silica glued to the mirrors on which the fibers will be mounted) have a residual inclination after their bonding we look for the four fibers that best compensate this initial inclination. As a result of this process, all the mirrors have a residual inclination under 1 mrad; Table 1 shows the values of all four test masses of AdV.

At low frequencies, the dynamical behavior of the suspending wire is simply represented by a three-segment model [6] (see Figure 4) whose parameters are the two lengths λ_t and λ_b , called bending lengths, and the distance L among these points, when the wire is loaded. An important request is that the top and the bottom bending points must lie on the horizontal planes passing through the

Figure 4: Scheme of the three-segment model of a silica wire. M and I_C are respectively the mass and the moment of inertia of the suspended mass. The model includes two angles ϕ and θ , describing the two low frequency resonances of the wire pendulum motion.

center of mass of the marionette and of the suspended mass, respectively, in order to minimize the longitudinal coupling

An important request is that both the top and bottom bending points must lie on the horizontal plane of the center of mass, respectively of the payload marionette and of the suspended mass to minimize the longitudinal coupling.

The bending points position of each fiber is measured with a machine that loads the fiber with the nominal load, and starts to rotate the upper clamp; at the same time the horizontal displacement of the lower part of the fiber is measured [7]. If the bending point is positioned in the center of rotation, there is no mechanical coupling between the upper clamp and the lower part of the fiber. The measurement procedure provides moving the center of rotation on the vertical axis and simultaneously measuring the horizontal displacement of the fiber. The position that minimizes this shift coincides with the bending point: the operating principle is shown in Figure 5. The same facility is used to measure the violin frequency by exciting the fiber and reading its vibration through a shadow meter placed in the center of the fiber [8].

Silica fibers production and characterization for the large masses of AdV+

The roadmap of AdV+ foresees to change the weight of the end mirrors, going from 42 kg to 105 kg, and this choice requires a new design of the silica fibers: in order to keep the same stress as for AdV (~ 800 MPa) the current diameter of the fibers must be increased by 60%, from $400 \mu\text{m}$ to $640 \mu\text{m}$. Some preliminary tests indicate that, even in the new configuration, the load stress will stay at least three times below the breaking strength, and the violin and bouncing frequencies will be virtually unchanged.

Figure 5: Measure of bending points position. The fiber is loaded and the upper rotate: if the bending point is exactly on the rotation axis (a) the lower part of the fibre does not move away from the vertical line. If the rotation center doesn't coincide with the bending point (b)(c) we measure an horizontal displacement.

Fabrication system

Thicker fibers need a slower production process, requiring a high stability in time of all the parameters involved. We measured that the the power of the CO_2 laser varies by of about $\pm 3\%$ in a timescale of about ten seconds, and this fluctuation may affect the thickness uniformity of the fibers during the laser polishing and the pulling process [9]. In order to increase the power stability we are planning to realize a close loop stabilization system that, by taking a part of the laser power, and measuring it through a sensor, is able to dynamically adjust the laser intensity. We will test also another control scheme, based on the feedback of a USB camera (with the suitable ND filter) reading the luminosity of the rod heated by the laser in order to estimate the power that hit the silica surface.

During the fiber production some vibrations are generated by the spin of the rotating mirror, so an optical system update is under development. This update consists in replacing the two rotating mirrors with an axicon and a conic mirror (Figure 6), in order to have no moving parts and therefore no sources of mechanical oscillations [10].

Characterization facilities

The new fibers require a new system to test their breaking load, thus a new machine with the possibility to load the fiber up to 200 kg has been built. However, when a fiber subjected to such a high load breaks, it is pulverized and also the silica clamps are destroyed, therefore it is impossible to identify the starting point of the break. This is a problem because during the test phase we want to establish if the possible trouble resides in the fiber or in the clamping or in the welding, which are all extremely critical parts. To overcome this issue we can use a fast camera during each test so that the exact breaking point can be located with certainty.

As far as profiling is concerned, we have developed a system based on a usb microscope mounted on a slider that can capture the image of the fiber for its whole length; using an edge detection algorithm we can measure the thickness of the fiber in every point. This measurement apparatus is important

Figure 6: The actual system with two rotating mirrors (left) and the updated system without rotating part (right).

in testing phase, when we will set the proper parameters in order to build fibers with the correct diameter at every point.

For the bending length measurement a new machine should be designed to support the weight of the new workload, but to avoid suspending the fibers with such a high load, we decided to use a mathematical model for an indirect estimation. A full description of the model can be found in [6]. Using a FEM solver and the measure of the thickness of the fiber (for this reason a good profiling system is important) it is possible to estimate with a very good approximation the bending point: the Figure 7 shows the good agreement between the measurement made with the method described in the previous section and the FEM estimation.

Fiber strength under fatigue

The fatigue failure in silica fibers has been studied for a long time, however the published results are not directly applicable to our case because silica fibers that we produce have far fewer superficial defects than those discussed in the literature. Even if different type of models have been considered [11], the Griffith theory [2] represents a starting point for our study. According to this theory the stress intensity factor K_I is introduced to describe the local stress intensification by surface defects or micro-cracks:

$$K_I = \sigma Y \sqrt{C} \quad (1)$$

where σ represents the applied stress, Y is a geometry factor that depends on the shape of the crack (typically ~ 1) and C represents the crack length. According to equation 1, the stress intensity factor is a function of the defect size and the applied stress. The maximum value that K_I can reach is called critical stress intensity factor (K_{IC}) and its value is a material dependent parameter: for fused silica $K_{IC} = 0.79 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$ [12]. When $K_I \geq K_{IC}$ a crack propagates and the fiber breaks; when $K_I < K_{IC}$ the relationship between the speed of crack growth and the other parameters is expressed by a power law [4]:

$$\frac{dC}{dt} = v_0 \left(\frac{K_I}{K_{IC}} \right)^n \quad (2)$$

where n and v_0 are empirical parameters.

Figure 7: Results comparison between the bending length measurement and a FEM estimation. The triangles show the measurement on the bending point machine. The lower triangle relates to the lower horizontal displacement of the fiber and therefore its abscissa represents the length of the bending point. The squares represent the estimated values of the mathematical model. The bending point measures for the two methods are $\lambda_t = (33.9 \pm 0.2)mm$ and $\lambda_t = (33.85 \pm 0.05)mm$ respectively for the experimental method and the FEM simulation.

Considering a static load applied to the fiber it is possible to achieve a solution to the model and get a formula for the lifetime of a fiber (T_s) :

$$T_s = \frac{2}{n-2} \frac{K_{IC}^2 S_i^{n-2}}{Y^2 v_0 \sigma^n} \quad (3)$$

with S_i is the inert strength, namely the stress needed to break the fiber when no crack growth takes place during the test itself.

This formula gives the lifetime of the fiber subjected to a static load, that is the normal status for those used in the monolithic suspensions. Our aim is to study the behavior of the fibers, but, since we expect very long lifetime with loads similar to working loads, we cannot wait for their completion and therefore the idea is to combine tests with static (high) load, with dynamic fatigue test. By developing the differential starting equation for a linearly varying load ($\dot{\sigma} = const$) we get the following result, under appropriate conditions:

$$S_f^{n+1} = 2 \frac{(n+1)}{n-2} \frac{K_{IC}^2 \dot{\sigma}}{v_0 Y^2} S_i^{n-2} \quad (4)$$

with S_f the final stress, that is the test breaking stress. Combining the information of both the approaches we are confident to ascertain if the power law model is correct to describe our fibers and we will also estimate its parameters. Beside maintenance and safety reasons, a quantitative knowledge of the aging of a fiber under load will help us to design the best proof test for the construction phase of AdV+.

Conclusions

The development of the future gravitational wave interferometers foresees larger test masses than those presently mounted in aLigo and AdV, in particular for AdV+ is planned to increase their weight by 2.5 times; this update impacts on the whole suspension and, obviously, on the silica fibers, whose diameter will be increased to support the new weight while maintaining the same safety constraints and the same resonant frequencies (violin and bouncing modes). We propose some improvements of the production system related to the laser power stabilization and the vibrations reduction; furthermore a new approach for the measurement of the bending point position is presented. Finally, we propose an approach to study the behavior of fibers subjected to fatigue so as to have a reliable model to estimate their life and the best proof test for their validation.

References

- [1] G. Cagnoli and P. Willems *Phys. Rev. B* **65**, 174111 (2002)
- [2] A.A. Griffith, *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London. Series A*, **221**, (2018)
- [3] S. L. Semjonov, G. S. Glaesemann, and M. M. Bubno *Proc. SPIE* **3848**, 3848 (1999)
- [4] M. J. Matthewson, *Review fo Scientific Instruments* **84**, 033904 (2013)
- [5] S. T. Yang et Al., *Applied Optics* **49**, 14 (2010)
- [6] F. Piergiovanni et Al., *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*. **228**, 012017 (2010)
- [7] M. Lorenzini et Al. *Proc SPIE* **CR50**, p. 3-31 (1994)
- [8] G. Cagnoli, L. Gammaitoni, J. Kovalik, F. Marchesoni, M. Punturo, *Phys. Lett. A* **213**, 245 1996.
- [9] K. Lee et Al. *Class. Quantum Grav.* **36**, 185018 (2019)
- [10] K. Toland et Al. *Class. Quantum Grav.* **35**, 165004 (2018)
- [11] L.K. Baker, *Corning White Paper* **5049**, (2001)
- [12] S. Semjonov and G. S. Glaesemann, *Micro and Opto-Electronic Materials and Structures: Physics, Mechanics, Design, Reliability, Packaging* , pp A595-A625 (2007)